

Note on the Action of Neutral Salts in Enzymatic Processes. The Effect of Bromides on Salivary Amylase.

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The effect of neutral salts on the action of amylases has been studied from a fairly long time, and it has been found that there is usually an accelerating action. A summary of the main literature may be found in Falk ("The Chemistry of Enzyme Action," 1924, pp. 106-109; compare also Sherman and Thomas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 623). This note deals mainly with the so-called anomalous effect of bromides on malt amylase as observed by Thomas (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1501). This author showed a number of years ago that sodium bromide at high concentrations activate the saccharogenic action of malt amylase, but at low concentrations retard this action, a fact in marked contrast with the effect of chlorides, nitrates or sulphate. No explanation was suggested nor any further results have appeared on this subject so far as the present writer is aware. Since the amylases from different sources vary somewhat in their action, and specially the optimal hydrogen ion concentrations are different for each, it was thought desirable to obtain some data with salivary amylase to see if a similar retarding effect of bromides is obtained or not.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Several samples of the amylase were collected from time to time from the human salivary excretion of the same source according to the method of Cole ("Practical Physiological Chemistry," 1921, p. 189). It was found that the amylase became gradually inactive on standing even at the laboratory temperature which never exceeded 20° during the day so far as its amyloclastic action was considered. Thus a sample of the amylase of a particular concentration gave a chronic period of 25 minutes on the first day, 35 minutes on the third day and over one hour on the seventh day. For the present

experiments therefore it was decided to make a series of experiments on the same day and simultaneously so as to get absolutely comparable results. Two different samples of the enzyme have been used which are denoted by numbers.

The amylolytic action has been determined by the so-called "Achromic Point" method, in which the chromic period or the time necessary to completely hydrolyse the starch into erythro-dextrin and maltose was obtained colourimetrically in presence of iodine. The sacharogenic action was studied by stopping the enzyme action at a particular time by adding alkali and then determining the reduction of Fehling's solution by Schoorl's (*Zeit. angew. Chem.*, 1899, p. 633) method. This method consists in determining the excess of cupric ion by addition of potassium iodide, acidifying and then titrating the liberated iodine by means of thiosulphate. According to Sutton ("Volumetric Analysis," 1911, p. 331) "results agreeing with gravimetric determinations can be obtained if a fair excess of potassium iodide be used, and if this be added to the alkaline liquid prior to acidification." Concordant results have been obtained by the writer by the use of this method. All the enzymatic experiments were carried out at a temperature of 40°C in a water-bath and in each experiment a volume of starch solution containing 0.1 gram of starch (Kablbau's soluble), neutral to litmus, was used.

The first experiment was done to determine the optimal pH for the enzyme used in these experiments, because there is a considerable divergence in this value among the recorded results. Thus Ringer and Trigt (*Zeit. physiol. Chem.*, 1912, 82, 484) give the value 6.0, Olsson (*Zeit. physiol. Chem.*, 1921, 117, 91) gives it as 6.4. Michaelis and Pechstein (*Biochem. Zeit.*, 1914, 59, 77) found 6.1-6.2 with a phosphate buffer, whilst Hahn and Michalik (*Zeit. Biol.*, 1921, 73, 10) found pH 6.6 with phosphate and 5.6 with acetate mixture. Cole ("Practical Physiological Chemistry," 1921, p. 187) gives the value 6.7 with phosphate mixture. In Table I, the amylolytic action of salivary amylase in presence of a phosphate buffer is shown. The total volume was 10 c.c. including 2 c.c. of the phosphate solution. The buffer solution was prepared according to the directions given in Clark ("Determination of Hydrogen Ions," 1922). The range between 5.8 to 6.8 was only observed. Some sodium chloride was added to activate the enzyme.

TABLE I.
NaCl=0.2 mole/litre,
Enzyme I=2 c.c.

pH .	Chromic period in minutes.	Remarks.
5.8	>55	Not further investigated.
6.0	55	
6.2	50	
6.4	45	
6.6	41	These two chromic periods were practically the same.
6.8	40	

The results show that the optimal pH for the amylolytic action lies in the neighbourhood of 6.7 which is in agreement with that of Cole and Hahn and Michalik. In Table II is shown the effect of sodium chloride on the enzyme activity.

TABLE II.
Enzyme II=4 c.c.
No buffer : Vol.=10 c.c.

Chromic period without NaCl.	Chromic period with NaCl 0.1 mole/litre.
5 Minutes	35 Minutes

From Table II it will be observed that the effect of NaCl is an accelerating one, and hence the enzyme is behaving in a normal way. The following Table III gives the chromic period with different amounts of primary phosphate. The results show that higher concentrations of the primary phosphate have a little beneficial action.

TABLE III.
NaCl=0.2 mol/litre; Enzyme I=2 c.c.
 $p_H = 6.8$: Vol. =10 c.c.

Conc. of buffer.	Chromic period in minutes.
0.5 c.c.	45
2.0 c. c.	40

These preliminary experiments showed that the enzyme effect was a perfectly normal one. The two following Tables IV and V now give the amyloclastic action of the amylase in presence of sodium and potassium bromides. Neither any buffer has been added in these experiments, nor any sodium chloride.

TABLE IV.

Effect of Potassium Bromide.

Enzyme II=4 c.c.

Conc. of bromide mole/litre.	Chromic period in minutes.
0.0	45
0.025	47
0.05	50
0.10	40

TABLE V.

Effect of Sodium Bromide.

(Same enzyme as in Table IV.)

0.0	45
0.025	45
0.05	50
0.10	50

These experiments show that with the concentration of the sodium bromide studied, the chromic period was in no case less than that in which no salt was added. With low concentration of potassium bromide a similar result was obtained, but with higher concentrations, an accelerating action was observed. This is in agreement with the observation of Thomas with malt amylase already mentioned. In the following two Tables VI and VII the saccharogenic effect is shown. No buffer was added in these cases also. The reaction was allowed to go on for exactly 15 minutes with enzyme I (Table VI) and 30 minutes with enzyme II (Table VII). The amount of reduction by pure starch has been deducted from the results given.

TABLE VI.

Enzyme I = 2 c.c. Vol. = 10 c.c.

Conc. of KBr (molar).	Reduction of Fehling's in terms of Cu_2O (milligrams).
0.0	28.596
0.05	19.064
0.15	11.915
0.20	16.681

TABLE VII.

Enzyme II = 4 c.c. Vol. = 12 c.c.

Conc. of NaBr (molar).	Reduction in terms of Cu_2O (milligrams).
0.0	104.8
0.0208	102.17
0.0416	90.55
0.0832	90.55
0.1664	90.55

These results show that with the concentrations of bromides studied in this paper and with the concentrations of the enzymes, the effect observed is one of depression in the activity of the enzyme. With higher concentrations of the salts possibly an augmenting action would be observed as in the case of amyloclastic action, but this has not been tried in the case of sacharogenic effect.

These experiments extend the results of Thomas to the case of salivary amylase. No satisfactory explanation of these can however be given at this place. A change in the degree of dispersion of the enzymes in presence of the salts may be one of the factors, as well as a change in the iso-electric point of the enzyme (*cf.* Hahn and Harpuder, *Zeit. Biol.*, 1920, 71, 302), but in some cases the effect is so specific that no general theory which explains all the individual cases can be given. A discussion of the theoretical aspects will be attempted along with further experiments in the next communication.

Summary.

- (1) The optimal p_H of salivary amylase is in the neighbourhood of 6.7 with phosphate buffer.
- (2) Bromides at low concentrations have a depressing effect on the amyloclastic and sacharogenic action of salivary amylase.

